

Atheist Philosophies of India: Jainism and Buddhism as a Rational Path to Spiritual Liberation and Social Reform in Ancient India

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Abstract

Jainism, one of the ancient religions of India, offers a comprehensive doctrinal system encompassing metaphysics, cosmology, theology, and ethics, which promotes rational thinking and discourages superstition. Rooted in the axiom that nothing is destructible, Jainism views the universe as eternal and uncreated, distinctly diverging from the Vedantic concept of a Creator. It categorizes life into Jiva (living beings) and Ajiva (non-living entities), with a unique understanding of karma that emphasizes self-responsibility and the inevitability of consequences. Jainism's conception of divinity is equally distinct, where liberated souls achieve God-like status without subscribing to the notion of a Supreme Creator. The religion emphasizes non-violence (Ahimsa), the multiplicity of viewpoints (Anekantavada), and non-possessiveness (Aparigraha) as cardinal principles. The rise of Jainism, alongside Buddhism, in the 6th century B.C. India can be attributed to the societal discontent with the ritualistic and caste-ridden practices of contemporary Hinduism. Both religions offered simpler, more accessible paths to spiritual fulfillment, challenging the established Brahmanical order and promoting a more egalitarian social structure.

Keywords: Atheism in India; Jainism and Buddhism; Social Reforms in Ancient India; Spiritual Liberation.

Full Text:

Jainism and Buddhism emerged in India during the 5th-6th century BC, not as mere corrections to existing Hinduism, but as significant departures or rebellions against how Hinduism was practiced at the time, which was unacceptable to a large portion of the population. The Brahmanical dominance, which had a firm grip on religious and social affairs, was increasingly rejected by many who found it unnecessary and oppressive. The rise of these two religions occurred primarily in what is now modern Bihar, a province whose very name is derived from the Buddhist term "Vihara," meaning monastery.

Despite their differences, Jainism and Buddhism shared a common foundation in opposing the rituals and practices dominated by the Brahman caste. Nearly 95% of the Indian population at the time eventually embraced either Buddhism or Jainism, though Hindu practices continued, primarily among the Brahman community. Both Mahavira, the proponent of Jainism, and Gautama Buddha, the founder of Buddhism, hailed from the region that is now Bihar. Jainism predates Buddhism, but both religions emphasized nonviolence, and truth, and rejected the animal sacrifices prevalent in Vedic rituals.

During the post-Vedic period, society was divided into four major classes based on labor: the Brahmanas (priests and teachers), Kshatriyas (warriors and rulers), Vaishyas (traders and agriculturists), and Sudras (servants and laborers). This division referred to as the "varna" system, was often associated with the color of one's skin—a notion rooted in the supposed distinctions between the Aryans and the Indigenous people they encountered. Brahmanas, who were responsible for religious duties, claimed the highest status and enjoyed numerous privileges, including exemptions from taxation and punishment. Kshatriyas, who ranked second, were tasked with governance and warfare, while Vaishyas engaged in commerce and agriculture, paying taxes to support the upper classes. The Sudras, placed at the bottom, were relegated to servitude and were often excluded from participating in religious and educational practices.

The rigid varna system inevitably generated social tensions, particularly among the Kshatriyas, who resisted the Brahmanical claim to supremacy. This resistance was one of the factors that led to the rise of new religious movements. Both Vardhamana Mahavira and Gautama Buddha, who belonged to the Kshatriya clan, challenged the authority of the Brahmanas. However, the deeper roots of these movements can be found in the spread of a new agricultural economy in northeastern India. This region, which includes parts of modern Uttar

Pradesh and Bihar, was initially covered with dense forests that could only be cleared with iron tools. The advent of iron tools around 600 B.C. enabled large-scale agricultural settlements, leading to significant social and economic changes.

The new agrarian economy, based on the use of iron plows and bullocks, required the preservation of cattle, which conflicted with the Vedic practice of cattle sacrifice. As agriculture became more central to the economy, the indiscriminate killing of cattle for rituals became increasingly impractical. Additionally, the rise of cities in northeastern India, such as Kaushambi, Kusinagar, Banaras, Vaishali, Chirand, and Rajgir, fostered a growing class of artisans and traders who began using coins and contributed to the importance of the Vaishya class. The Vaishyas placed third in the varna hierarchy, sought a religion that would improve their social standing. Jainism and Buddhism, with their rejection of the varna system and their promotion of nonviolence, appealed to both the Kshatriyas and Vaishyas.

The merchants, known as Setthis, supported these new religions generously. Jainism and Buddhism's initial disregard for the varna system, their advocacy of nonviolence, and their opposition to the Brahmanical disdain for moneylending made them attractive to the commercial class. At the same time, these new forms of property and wealth created social inequalities, leading some to yearn for a return to a simpler, ascetic life. Both religions emphasized a life of purity and renunciation, rejecting the materialism and luxury associated with urban and commercial life.

Jainism, according to tradition, dates back to ancient times, with a line of 24 Tirthankaras, or spiritual teachers, the last of whom was Mahavira, a contemporary of Buddha. Jainism preached five core doctrines: nonviolence, truthfulness, non-stealing, non-possession, and celibacy, with nonviolence being the most emphasized. Jainism's strict asceticism led to a division into two sects: the Shvetambaras, who wore white clothes, and the Digambaras, who practiced nudity. Unlike Buddhism, Jainism did not outright reject the varna system but offered a more flexible approach, allowing for spiritual progress regardless of caste.

Despite its limited appeal compared to Buddhism, Jainism spread gradually, especially in southern and western India, where Brahmanical influence was weaker. Jainism's adoption of Prakrit, a language of the common people, helped in spreading its teachings. Although Jainism did not spread as rapidly as Buddhism, it left a lasting impact on art, architecture, and literature, particularly in regions like Karnataka, Gujarat, and Rajasthan.

Gautama Buddha, born Siddhartha in 563 B.C. in a Shakya Kshatriya family, renounced his princely life in search of a solution to human suffering. After attaining enlightenment under a pipal tree in Bodh Gaya, he preached a practical path to end suffering, known as the Eightfold Path. Buddhism rejected the existence of a supreme God and the soul (Atman), which was revolutionary in Indian religious thought. It offered a more egalitarian approach, attracting people from all castes, including women, and spread rapidly across non-Vedic areas.

Buddhism's emphasis on the middle path between luxury and asceticism, and its appeal to the lower castes and non-Vedic populations, contributed to its widespread acceptance. However, while Buddhism gradually declined in India, largely due to the revival of Hinduism and the spread of Islamic invasions, Jainism maintained a presence in certain regions.

In summary, the rise of Jainism and Buddhism in India was a response to the socio-economic changes of the time, particularly the new agricultural economy and the dissatisfaction with the Varna system. Both religions offered alternatives to the rigid Brahmanical order and played crucial roles in shaping India's religious and cultural landscape.

The spread of Buddhism was significantly aided by the use of Pali, the language of the common people, which made Buddhist teachings accessible to the masses. Gautama Buddha also established the Sangha, or religious order, which welcomed individuals regardless of caste or gender. The only requirement for joining the Sangha was adherence to its rules and regulations. Once they became members of the Buddhist community, monks were expected to take vows of celibacy, poverty, and faithfulness to the teachings. The three main elements of Buddhism—Buddha, Sangha, and Dhamma—were central to its rapid expansion. Through organized preaching under the Sangha, Buddhism gained widespread acceptance during Buddha's lifetime. Monarchies in Magadha, Koshala, Kaushambi, and several republican states adopted the religion.

Two hundred years after Buddha's death, the Mauryan king Ashoka embraced Buddhism, an event of great historical significance. Ashoka's efforts to spread Buddhism through his emissaries helped transform it into a

global religion, reaching Central Asia, West Asia, and Sri Lanka. Today, Buddhism remains a major religion in countries like Sri Lanka, Myanmar, Tibet, and parts of China and Japan. Although Buddhism eventually declined in India, its influence endures in many parts of Asia.

By the early 12th century A.D., Buddhism had nearly vanished from India. It persisted in altered forms in Bengal and Bihar until the 11th century, but eventually, it almost completely disappeared. Several factors contributed to this decline. Initially, like many religions, Buddhism began as a reform movement but gradually succumbed to the very rituals and ceremonies it had once criticized. Over time, Buddhism absorbed many of the practices of Brahmanism, the dominant religion it had originally opposed. The Brahmanas, in response to the Buddhist challenge, reformed their practices, emphasizing the preservation of cattle wealth and promising women and Sudras admission to heaven. Meanwhile, Buddhism deteriorated, with monks becoming increasingly detached from the lives of ordinary people as they abandoned Pali in favor of Sanskrit, the language of intellectuals.

From the first century A.D. onwards, Buddhist monks began practicing widespread idol worship and accepting large offerings from devotees. The growing wealth of Buddhist monasteries, some of which received revenue from as many as 200 villages, led to corruption and a decline in discipline. By the 7th century A.D., many monasteries had become centers of indulgence, contrary to the austere principles taught by Gautama Buddha. This new form of Buddhism, known as Vajrayana, was marked by the accumulation of wealth and the presence of women in monasteries, which further contributed to the religion's decline.

Buddhism also faced persecution from rulers who favored Brahmanism. For instance, the Brahmana ruler Pushyamitra Shunga and the Huna king Mihirakula, a devotee of Shiva, are said to have persecuted Buddhists. In South India, Shaivites and Vaishnavites opposed both Jainism and Buddhism during the early medieval period, further weakening the religion. The wealth of Buddhist monasteries made them targets for Turkish invaders, who destroyed many of these institutions and killed a large number of monks. By the 12th century A.D., Buddhism had largely disappeared from India, though it left a lasting impact on the country's history.

Despite its decline, Buddhism made significant contributions to Indian society. It addressed the social and economic inequalities of the time, advising against the accumulation of wealth, which Buddha believed bred hatred, cruelty, and violence. To mitigate these evils, he advocated providing farmers with grain, traders with wealth, and laborers with wages. Buddhism also introduced a new intellectual and cultural awareness, encouraging people to question and reason rather than accept things on faith alone. This rationalist approach helped diminish superstition and promote logical thinking.

Buddhist literature, written in Pali, played a crucial role in spreading the religion's teachings. The early Pali literature is divided into three categories: the sayings and teachings of the Buddha, the rules for members of the Sangha, and the philosophical exposition of the Dhamma. Later, by blending Pali with Sanskrit, Buddhist scholars created Hybrid Sanskrit, which further enriched the language. Buddhist monasteries, such as those at Nalanda and Vikramashila in Bihar and Valabhi in Gujarat, developed into great centers of learning, akin to residential universities.

Buddhism also left a profound impact on Indian art. The first human statues worshiped in India were likely those of the Buddha. Artists depicted various events from Buddha's life in stone panels, with notable examples found at Gaya in Bihar and at Sanchi and Bharhut in Madhya Pradesh. From the first century A.D. onwards, images of Gautama Buddha became common. The collaboration between Greek and Indian sculptors in the northwest frontier of India led to the development of Gandhara art, which combined Indian and foreign influences. The creation of monasteries in rock-hewn caves marked the beginning of cave architecture, with notable examples in the Barabar Hills in Gaya and western India around Nasik.

The rise of Buddhism is closely tied to the prevailing practices of Brahmanical religion (early Hinduism). Brahmanism had become increasingly exclusive, primarily benefiting Brahmins and the aristocracy, and heavily dependent on rituals conducted by priests. Sanskrit, the language of the Brahmins, was inaccessible to the common people. In contrast, Buddha's teachings offered an alternative that was accessible to the masses, particularly merchants and Sudras (untouchables), by using Prakrit, a language spoken by the people. Buddhism provided a straightforward path to salvation, free from the complex rituals of Brahmanism.

Buddha established monasteries, known as Sanghas, with rules for monks that required renunciation of worldly life and dependence on the generosity of the lay community. Monks lived ascetically, shaving their heads and wearing simple saffron robes. The growth of Buddhism was fueled by support from the general

population and royal patronage. Monastic orders were often located near settlements and trade routes, allowing monks to interact with merchants who provided donations in exchange for shelter.

After Buddha's death, stupas, or mounds, were constructed to hold his relics and ashes, becoming symbols of veneration. Over time, Buddhism evolved into two main sects: Mahayana and Hinayana. Mahayana Buddhism, which elevated Buddha to the status of a god and permitted his representation in human form, eventually became more popular and spread to Southeast Asia and China. Hinayana Buddhism, on the other hand, remained closer to the original teachings of Buddha.

By the 6th century A.D., Mahayana Buddhism had spread to Cambodia and Thailand, and by 50 A.D., it had reached China. Followers of Buddhism believe that its roots in India predate those of Brahmanism, which they associate with Aryan migrants from outside India. Some even suggest that Jainism, with its emphasis on non-violence (Ahimsa), has roots in the ancient Indus Valley Civilization. However, conclusive evidence linking these beliefs to the origins of Hinduism remains elusive.

Jainism, like Buddhism, places a strong emphasis on non-violence and strict discipline. Jain householders are expected to evolve into monks later in life, following a path similar to that of Vedic-era Hinduism. The first Tirthankara, Rishabhdev, is believed to have lived before the Indus Valley Civilization and is mentioned in both Jain and Hindu texts, highlighting the interconnectedness of the two religions in ancient times.

Jainism flourished in regions like Magadha, where its teachings influenced rulers and the broader society. However, over time, divisions arose within the Jain community, leading to the formation of sects such as the Shvetambaras and Digambaras. Despite these divisions, Jainism continued to thrive, especially in South India and Gujarat, where it remains a significant religious tradition.

In conclusion, while Buddhism eventually declined in India, its impact on art, culture, and society was profound and enduring. Jainism, on the other hand, maintained a continuous presence in India, influencing various aspects of Indian life and thought.

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Jainism, being one of the ancient religions of India, has developed a comprehensive doctrinal system that includes metaphysics, cosmology, theology, and ethics. It discourages superstition and blind faith, promoting instead free and rational thinking.

1. Metaphysics and Ontology

Jainism begins with the axiom that nothing is destructible—nothing can be created from nothing—similar to the Samkhya philosophy. The universe is uncreated, real, and eternal, existing without a beginning or end, differing from the Vedantic concept of a Creator.

In Jainism, the universe consists of two fundamental categories: **Jiva** (living beings) and **Ajiva** (non-living entities). Jiva refers to an infinite number of souls, while Ajiva is divided into five categories: (a) matter (pudgala), (b) medium of motion (dharma), (c) medium of rest (adharma), (d) space (akasha), and (e) time (kala).

2. Classes of Jivas (Souls)

Souls in Jainism are categorized into two kinds: **Mukta** (liberated souls) and **Samsara** (mundane or embodied souls). Samsara souls are further classified into mobile and immobile. Immobile souls, found in elements like earth, water, fire, air, and vegetation, possess only one sense organ. Unlike in Hinduism, where elements like air and water are considered inert, Jainism attributes life or soul to these elements.

Mobile beings vary in the number of sense organs, ranging from two to five, and only a few of the five-sensed beings have the faculties of mind and intelligence. Samsara souls undergo cycles of birth and death until they attain nirvana.

3. The Karma Doctrine

Jainism's karma doctrine is distinct from that of Hinduism. In Jainism, karma is viewed as a subtle matter that attaches to the soul when it is influenced by attachment (raga) or aversion (dvesha). This karmic matter is of two types: **Bhava karmas** (related to feelings, emotions, and passions) and **Dravya karmas** (material forms). To liberate the soul from karmic matter, one must perform satvik (pure) actions.

The Jain theory of karma is based on the law of cause and effect, which asserts that every action has consequences that must be borne, sooner or later. This theory explains the diversities in physical and mental conditions at birth and supports the concept of the transmigration of souls. It emphasizes that individuals are responsible for their fate, inspiring them to purify their souls through willpower and righteous actions.

4. Divinity

In Jainism, divinity is unique. Each soul, upon freeing itself from karmic matter, becomes **Svambhu** and attains a state of highest spiritual evolution. Jain divinities are categorized into **Siddhas** (absolutely liberated souls) and **Arhatas** (those who have attained emancipation or Jivan Mukta). Siddhas represent the ultimate state of liberation, while Arhatas, also known as Kevalins or Jinas, are revered for their spiritual achievements. Unlike the Vedantic philosophy, Jainism does not view God as the First Cause. However, it recognizes a pantheon of celestial beings similar to Hindu gods, who are also considered mortal.

5. Pragmatic Optimism

Jainism views the world as a "vale of tears," filled with suffering, struggle, and anxiety. However, it also offers a path to transcend these difficulties by attaining nirvana, the end of the soul's journey.

6. Idol Worship

Like Hinduism, Jainism practices idol worship. The Tirthankaras, particularly Lord Mahavira, who was born on March 30, 599 B.C., and attained nirvana in 527 B.C., are central figures in Jain worship. Mahavira, the 24th and last Tirthankara, significantly shaped the present form of Jainism.

Cardinal Principles of Jainism

The core principles of Jainism are:

1. **Ahimsa** (non-violence)
2. **Anekantavada** (multiplicity of views)
3. **Aparigraha** (non-possessiveness)
4. **Non-stealing**
5. **Brahmacharya** (celibacy)

Anekantavada is particularly noteworthy as it promotes tolerance and the understanding that multiple perspectives can contribute to a fuller knowledge of any subject. This concept is illustrated by the famous story of the blind men and the elephant, where each man's description of the elephant is correct but incomplete. Jainism teaches that an object can be described by seemingly opposite statements depending on the substance, place, time, and form, a method of understanding known as **Asti-Nasti-Vada**.

Syadvada or the doctrine of "maybe" introduces an element of uncertainty and probability in predictions, emphasizing that truth can be viewed from different perspectives.

Jainism and Vedanta, while different, do not necessarily contradict each other. Jainism simplifies the complexities of the universe for practical understanding, while Vedanta delves into the depths of creation, leading to the concept of God as the First Cause. Jainism, with its emphasis on non-violence and respect for all forms of life, advocates a way of life that influences every aspect of human conduct.

In summary, Jainism upholds the highest ideal of the Tirthankara, who possesses infinite knowledge, bliss, and power. Tirthankaras are akin to divine beings in Jainism, taking the place of God in other religions. Jainism makes a distinction between **Arhat** and **Siddha**, which parallels the Vedantic concepts of **Jivan Mukta** (liberated in life) and **Videha Mukta** (liberated from the body). Tirthankaras, who preach the truth during their lifetime, represents the pinnacle of spiritual achievement in Jainism.

Historical and Religious Significance of Vaishali

Vaishali, dating back to pre-historic times, holds great significance in Jainism, Buddhism, and Hinduism. According to Puranas, it was named after King Vishala and became a prominent religious center during Lord Mahavira's time. The city, surrounded by three walls with gates and watchtowers, was known for its prosperity and democratic governance.

Both Lord Mahavira and Lord Buddha were closely connected to Vaishali. Mahavira obtained enlightenment on Mount Vipul at Rajgir, while Buddha visited the city several times during his life, initially seeking a guru. The city maintained its importance for centuries, serving as a key site for religious and political activities.

Causes of the Rise of Jainism and Buddhism in 6th Century B.C.

Several factors contributed to the rise of Jainism and Buddhism in India during the 6th century B.C.:

1. **Rigidity and Ritualism in Hinduism:** Over time, the simple Vedic religion became complex and ritualistic, alienating many people who longed for a simpler faith.
2. **Costly Rituals:** The elaborate and expensive rituals of later Vedic religion were burdensome, prompting a desire for a more accessible religion.
3. **Animal Sacrifice:** The practice of animal sacrifice in Yajnas was opposed by many who sought a religion that preached non-violence.
4. **Belief in Magic and Charms:** The growing reliance on charms and magic led progressive thinkers to reject these practices and seek a more rational religion.
5. **Supremacy of the Brahman Priests:** The hereditary Brahman class began to be seen as corrupt and morally degenerate, leading to a loss of faith in their authority.
6. **Difficult Language:** Sanskrit, the language of religious texts, was inaccessible to the common people, creating a demand for religious teachings in a simpler language.
7. **Caste System:** The rigid caste system created deep social divisions, with low-caste individuals seeking a religion that promoted equality.

8. **Efforts of Learned Scholars:** The teachings of Mahavira and Buddha, which emphasized simplicity and equality, naturally attracted those disillusioned with the existing social and religious order.

These factors collectively led to the emergence of Jainism and Buddhism as major religious movements that challenged the existing order and offered new paths to spiritual and social fulfillment.

Conclusion

Jainism presents a profound philosophical and ethical framework that has influenced Indian thought for millennia. Its doctrines, particularly those related to non-violence and karma, provide a distinct perspective on the human condition and the nature of existence. Jainism's emphasis on rationality, ethical conduct, and spiritual self-reliance distinguishes it from other Indian philosophies, particularly in its rejection of a Supreme Creator and its focus on the individual's journey to liberation. The rise of Jainism, along with Buddhism, in ancient India was a response to the social and religious challenges of the time, offering an alternative to the rigid and exclusionary practices of Vedic religion. Despite its ancient origins, Jainism's teachings remain relevant, continuing to inspire adherents to live lives of non-violence, humility, and ethical integrity.

References:

- Jaini, Padmanabh S. *The Jaina Path of Purification*. University of California Press, 1979.
- Dundas, Paul. *The Jains*. Routledge, 2002.
- Jain, Champat Rai. *The Practical Path*. Jain Literature Society, 1933.
- Zimmer, Heinrich. *Philosophies of India*. Princeton University Press, 1951.
- Sangave, Vilas Adinath. *Jain Community: A Social Survey*. Popular Prakashan, 1980.
- Bhargava, Dayanand. *Jain Ethics*. Motilal Banarsidass, 1968.
- Laidlaw, James. *Riches and Renunciation: Religion, Economy, and Society among the Jains*. Clarendon Press, 1995.
- Williams, Robert R. *Jaina Yoga: A Survey of the Mediaeval Śrāvaka-cāras*. Motilal Banarsidass, 1983.
